

EFFICACY OF SHORT COURSE ORAL CORTICOSTEROIDS WITH ORAL ACYCLOVIR VERSUS ORAL ACYCLOVIR ALONE IN THE TREATMENT OF HERPES ZOSTER TO PREVENT POST HERPETIC NEURALGIA

Dr. Rubab Ayesha Rasheed¹, Dr. Aisha Akhtar², Dr. Uzma Bashir³,
Dr. Amna Naseer⁴, Dr. Rubina Kouser⁵, Dr. Kaneez Fatima⁶

¹Postgraduate Resident, Department of Dermatology, PEMH Rawalpindi

²Associate Professor of Dermatology, AFPGMI Rawalpindi, Department of Dermatology, PEMH Rawalpindi

³Associate Professor of Dermatology, AFPGMI Rawalpindi, Department of Dermatology, CMH Gujranwala

⁴Postgraduate Resident, Department of General Surgery, DHQ Hospital Mirpur AJK

⁵Postgraduate Resident, Department of Pediatrics, CMH Muzaffarabad AJK

⁶Postgraduate Resident, Department of Dermatology, PEMH Rawalpindi

¹rubabayesharashed@gmail.com

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19629870>

Keywords

Herpes zoster, Post herpetic neuralgia, oral corticosteroids

Article History

Received: 10 April 2025

Accepted: 12 April 2025

Published: 30 April 2025

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Corresponding Author: *

Dr Rubab Ayesha Rasheed

Abstract

Objective: To investigate the Efficacy of short course oral corticosteroids with oral acyclovir versus oral acyclovir alone in the treatment of herpes zoster to prevent post herpetic neuralgia.

Study design: It was a quasi-experimental study.

Place and duration: It was conducted at Pak Emirates military hospital Rawalpindi, from 1st April 2024 to 1st October 2024.

Methods: Forty-six patients diagnosed with acute HZ were divided into two equal groups: Group A receiving oral antivirals with oral corticosteroids and Group B receiving oral antivirals alone for a duration of 9 days each. Pain was assessed at multiple time points in follow up period using the Visual Analogue Scale (VAS) for up to 90 days. IBM SPSSv26 was used to run statistical tests including Wilcoxon signed-rank and Mann-Whitney U.

Results: All 46 patients followed up (23 in each group). The number of patients presenting with herpes zoster infection within 7 days was 19 (50%) in the non-corticosteroid group and 19 (50%) in the corticosteroid group; males were 20 (48.8%) and 21 (51.2%), respectively. There was a significant reduction in pain in both groups from Day 0 to Day 90 ($p < 0.001$), with 34(73.9%), 41(89.1%), and 45(97.8%) patients' pain-free on Days 7, 30, and 90, respectively. There was no statistically significant difference in VAS pain scores between the corticosteroid and non-corticosteroid groups at baseline ($p = 0.736$) or at Day 90 ($p = 0.317$).

Conclusion: The combination therapy does not significantly impact long-term outcomes.

Introduction

Herpes zoster (HZ) is an acute viral dermatological illness due to reactivation of the varicella zoster virus within the dorsal root or cranial nerve ganglia that presents as painful vesicular rash. [1,2] Post-herpetic neuralgia (PHN) is a debilitating

condition that arises as a complication of herpes zoster, commonly known as shingles. It is predominantly an illness of old age with 30% occurrence in age group >80 years and 20% in age group 60 to 65 years but rarely below 50 years of age.[3] Post herpetic pain can appear as cutaneous

allodynia, hyperpathia and dysesthesia.[4] PHN is characterized by persistent neuropathic pain that occurs after the resolution of the shingles rash. The pain can be severe, prolonged, and significantly impact the quality of life for affected individuals. Various treatment approaches have been explored, with a growing interest in combining antiviral drugs and corticosteroids to mitigate PHN symptoms. Antivirals, such as acyclovir, famciclovir, and valacyclovir, target the replication of the varicella-zoster virus (VZV), which causes shingles. Early initiation of antiviral therapy during the acute phase of shingles has been shown to reduce the severity and duration of the illness. The hypothesis that antivirals may also impact the development of post-herpetic neuralgia has spurred research into their extended benefits. Low-dose, short-term corticosteroids, such as prednisolone, have anti-inflammatory properties that may contribute to pain relief. These agents modulate the immune response, potentially suppressing inflammation around nerve fibers affected by the herpes zoster virus. The combination of antivirals and corticosteroids aims to address both the viral replication and the inflammatory response, offering a comprehensive approach to managing PHN.

A study done before by David W Wareham et al showed that corticosteroids with anti-virus therapy decrease severity of post herpetic neuralgia and speed up vesicle healing.[5] Contradictory to this a Cochrane review found that middle dose corticosteroids do not prevent PHN.[6] To solve this dilemma of whether there is a reduction in incidence and severity of PHN with addition of oral steroids to antivirals in management of herpes zoster, we conducted this study to find the synergistic effects of antiviral medications with low-dose (30mg prednisolone/day), short-term (<9 days) oral corticosteroids and their potential role in alleviating post-herpetic neuralgia.

Material and Methods

A quasi-experimental study was conducted in Dermatology outdoor and indoor patient department at Pakistan Emirates Military Hospital Rawalpindi Pakistan from 1st April 2024 to 1stOctober 2024. 46 patients meeting the criteria of post herpetic neuralgia, were enrolled according to the following inclusion and exclusion criteria:[7]

Inclusion criteria included patients with acute HZ diagnosed clinically with active lesions, who had no prior treatment, patients who gave informed consent and willing to be contacted on telephone for follow-up data. Exclusion criteria included, patients with severe organ dysfunction affecting the heart, liver or kidneys, patients with diabetes mellitus, active gastrointestinal ulcer, glaucoma, or other contraindications to corticosteroids, who reported after lesions had resolved with scarring, pregnant females and children less than 18 year of age.

Sample size was calculated according to sample size formula based on disease prevalence 2.4% [8], 95% confidence interval and at precision of 0.05. Sample size was calculated using single population proportion formula.[9] $n = Z^2 P(1-P) / d^2$

It was a non-random purposive sampling technique to study the effect of additional intervention in our study group. Patients assigned group A received tablet prednisolone starting at 30mg per day for the initial three days, then 20mg per day for three days, and 10mg per day for three days along with tab acyclovir 800mg five times a day for nine days, while patients in Group B were given tab acyclovir in the same dose as group A for 9 days and followed for 90 days through Visual Analogue Scale (VAS). Both groups received oral NSAIDs in same dose and topical cooling and drying lotions. Pain was assessed using the Visual Analogue Scale (VAS) on Days 0, 7, 30, and 90. As per the VAS grades were given; unbearable pain affecting daily life (severe pain, 7-10 points), tolerable pain affecting sleep (moderate pain 4-6 points) and tolerable slight pain (mild pain 0-3 points) [10]. Patients were contacted through telephone in these three months and incidence of PHN and adverse effects were documented

Data was analyzed using SPSS 26. nWilcoxon Signed-Rank Test was used to compare within-group differences between Day 0 and Day 90. Mann-Whitney U Test was used for between-group comparison on Day 90. Median (IQR) was used to express quantitative data. Significance was set at $p < 0.05$. Frequency and percentages were used for categorical data.

Results

Baseline demographic features were similar in both groups (Table 1). Most patients had presented within 7 days of disease onset (19 (50%)

in the non-corticosteroid and 19 (50%) in the corticosteroid group). Both groups had more males (20(48.8%) vs. 21(51.2%)). The majority of patients were aged <50 years (16(50%) vs. 16(50%)), with only group B having patients >70 years old (2(100%)). The trunk was the most common location of herpes zoster infection, 10(50%) in head and 13 (50%) in trunk, having equal occurrence in both groups. Limbs were not involved in any cases. Table 2 and table 3 showed a step-wise reduction in both groups. At baseline, patients generally had moderate pain (VAS 4-6). By Day 7, 34(73.9%) of patients were pain-free, which increased to 41 (89.1%) by Day 30 and 45(97.8%) by Day 90.

Table 4 shows Within group comparison with Wilcoxon Signed-Rank Test revealed a significant decrease in pain from Day 0 to Day 90. in both acyclovir-alone and corticosteroid groups (both p

< 0.001), with all patients experiencing improvement.

Table 5 shows between group comparison through the use of the Mann-Whitney U Test, indicated no statistically significant difference in VAS pain scores between the corticosteroid and non-corticosteroid groups at baseline (p = 0.736) or at Day 90 (p = 0.317).

Therefore, although both treatment courses were successful in providing pain resolution, the incorporation of corticosteroids with acyclovir did not offer any additional long-term benefit. There were significant intra-group reductions in pain for both groups but between-group comparison through the use of the Mann-Whitney U Test indicated no significant difference in VAS scores in the two groups at Day 90.

Antiviral therapy plus short term, low dose corticosteroid has no effect on incidence or severity of post herpetic neuralgia.

Table 1: Baseline characteristics of patients in the two groups

Variable	Category	Non-corticosteroid n (%)	Corticosteroid n (%)	Total n (%)
Course of disease duration	< 7 days	19 (50)	19 (50)	38 (100)
	> 7 days	4(50)	4 (50)	8(100)
Gender	Male	20 (48.8)	21 (51.2)	41 (89.1)
	Female	3 (60.0)	2 (40.0)	5 (10.8)
Age group (years)	< 50	16(50)	16 (50)	33 (71.7)
	50-70	7(58.3)	5 (41.7)	11 (23.9)
	> 70	0 (0.0)	2 (100.0)	2 (4.3)
HZ location	Head	10 (50.0)	10 (50.0)	20 (43.4)
	Trunk	13 (50.0)	13 (50.0)	26 (56.5)
	Limbs	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)

Data are presented as count (percentage). Percentages are calculated within each category of the characteristic. There were no missing values for any variable.

Table 2: VAS pain score on day 0, 7, 30 and 90 in test group A

VAS Score	Day 0 n (%)	Day 7 n (%)	Day 30 n (%)	Day 90 n (%)
0	0	18 (78.3)	22 (95.7)	23 (100)
1	0	0	0	0
2	4 (17.4)	1 (4.3)	0	0
3	4 (17.4)	2 (8.7)	0	0
4	4 (17.4)	2 (8.7)	1 (4.3)	0

VAS Score	Day 0 n (%)	Day 7 n (%)	Day 30 n (%)	Day 90 n (%)
5	8 (34.8)	0	0	0
6	3 (13.0)	0	0	0
7	0	0	0	0
8	0	0	0	0
9	0	0	0	0
10	0	0	0	0
Total	23 (100)	23 (100)	23 (100)	23 (100)

Data are presented as frequency (percentage). VAS = Visual Analog Scale for pain (0 = no pain, 10 = worst pain). Percentages are calculated for total participants at each time point (n=46).

Table 3: VAS pain score on day 0, 7, 30 and 90 in test group B

VAS Score	Day 0 n (%)	Day 7 n (%)	Day 30 n (%)	Day 90 n (%)
0	0	16 (69.6)	19 (82.6)	22 (95.7)
1	0	0	0	1 (4.3)
2	4 (17.4)	2 (8.7)	0	0
3	4 (17.4)	3 (13.0)	2 (8.7)	0
4	5 (21.7)	1 (4.3)	1 (4.3)	0
5	5 (21.7)	0	0	0
6	3 (13.0)	0	0	0
7	0	0	0	0
8	1 (4.3)	1 (4.3)	1 (4.3)	0
9	1 (4.3)	0	0	0
10	0	0	0	0
Total	23 (100)	23 (100)	23 (100)	23 (100)

Data are presented as frequency (percentage). VAS = Visual Analog Scale for pain (0 = no pain, 10 = worst pain). Percentages are calculated for total participants at each time point (n=46).

Table 4: n Wilcoxon Signed-Rank Test group A and B (Day 0 vs. Day 90)

Group	Variable	N	Day 0 Median (IQR)	Day 90 Median (IQR)	Z value	p value
Group A	VAS pain score	23	4.0 (2.0)	0.0 (0.0)*	-4.226	<0.001
Group B	VAS pain score	23	4.0 (2.0)	0.0 (0.0)	-4.182	<0.001

Data are presented as median (interquartile range, IQR). Within-group comparisons between Day 0 and Day 90 were performed using the Wilcoxon signed-rank test. *VAS pain score at Day 90 in Group A was constant; therefore, IQR equals zero. $p < 0.05$ was considered statistically significant.

Table 5: Mann-Whitney U Test between group A and B (Day 90).

Treatment Group	N	Median (IQR) Day 0	Median (IQR) Day 90	p value (Mann-Whitney U)
Group A	23	4.0 (2.0)	0.0 (0.0)*	0.736
Group B	23	4.0 (2.0)	0.0 (0.0)	0.317

Data are presented as median (interquartile range, IQR). Between-group comparisons were performed using the Mann-Whitney U test. *VAS pain score at Day 90 in Group A was constant; therefore, IQR equals zero. $p < 0.05$ was considered statistically significant.

Discussion

PHN is one of the most debilitating after effects of herpes zoster infection and can last for up to six months after the acute illness.[11] The pathogenesis of this complication is currently not that well known, although it is largely believed to be because of abnormal sympathetic nervous system, inflammatory response, decreased immune factors and central nervous system sensitization.[12] One hypothesis is that nerve injury due to VZV which causes increased erethism of spinal cord neurons and peripheral transmission fibers[13]. as per Yao-Tsung Lin et al, post herpetic neuralgia is due to persistent active VZV infection in the ganglion.[14] A study published in British journal of dermatology, Kecskes et al. compared effects of oral prednisolone 40mg slowly tapered over the period of 4 weeks and oral carbamazepine 100mg four times daily on the incident and duration of post herpetic neuralgia, with 15 percent of the patients on prednisolone developed post herpetic neuralgia lasting up to 6 months as compare to carbamazepine group in which 65 percent of patients developed post herpetic neuralgia lasting up to 2 years thus believing that corticosteroids are effective in preventing PHN. [14,15] Contrary to this believe a study published in 2013, Han Y et al. the results showed moderate doses of corticosteroids were effective in relieving acute pain of HZ but no effect on PHN. [16,17,18] The results of the above study were further strengthened by a Cochrane study carried out in 2023 Jiang X et al. that concluded that they were undetermined about the effects of corticosteroids administered orally during an acute herpes zoster infection on preventing postherpetic neuralgia.[19]. Wang Y et al. carried out a review on the studies on herpes zoster-associated pain in non-oral drug therapy which also included studies

regarding administration of intrathecal corticosteroids which did not show any significant improvement from control.[20] In this research, we compared the effectiveness of oral acyclovir monotherapy with oral acyclovir plus corticosteroids in herpes zoster patients. Both regimens resulted in significant improvement in pain over time, with complete resolution of pain by Day 90 in all patients. The inclusion of corticosteroids therefore did not confer any added long-term advantage over acyclovir monotherapy in our study.

Our results are concordant with V Esmann et al., a randomized, double blind, controlled study of effect of prednisolone on the development of post herpetic neuralgia in patients with herpes zoster which have proven that although corticosteroids can temporarily relieve acute pain and suppress inflammation in herpes zoster, they don't meaningfully change the long-term disease course or prevent post-herpetic neuralgia.[21] The similar results of the two groups in this study confirm the minimal role of corticosteroids as an adjunct to antiviral treatment, especially in light of their possible side effects in older or comorbid individuals.

The strengths of the current study are a well-matched comparison between two clinically relevant regimens and objective measurement of pain by VAS scale.

The limitations of our study include a relatively small sample size, non-randomized study design and a single study center.

Conclusion

The exploration of antivirals in tandem with low-dose, short-term corticosteroids for post-herpetic neuralgia is an evolving field. Although both groups showed improvement, no significant difference was found between them at 90 days.

The combination therapy does not significantly impact long-term outcomes.

Conflict of interest

None.

Statement of Ethics:

This research was performed in accordance with relevant guidelines and written informed consent was obtained from all participants or their legal guardians. This study was approved by Ethics Committee of Pakistan Emirates Military Hospital, Rawalpindi Pakistan (NO. A/28/ERC/97/24) and conducted ethically in accordance with the World Medical Association Declaration of Helsinki.

Authors Contribution

Author 1

Substantial contributions to study design, acquisition of data

Analysis & Interpretation of Data, Manuscript writing

Has given final approval of the version to be published

Agree to be accountable for all aspects of the work in ensuring that questions related to the accuracy

or integrity of any part of the work are appropriately investigated and resolved

Author 2,3,4,5,6

Substantial contributions to concept, study design Data Analysis, Manuscript writing, Critical Review

Has given final approval of the version to be published

Agree to be accountable for all aspects of the work in ensuring that questions related to the accuracy

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